

Preparation and Characterisation of Nickel(II) and Chromium(III) Complexes with *N*-Acylamino Acids and their Adducts

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Complexes of the type NiL_2XH_2O , adducts of the type $NiL_2B_nXH_2O$, $Cr^{III}L_3OH_2XH_2O$ and $Cr^{III}L_3XH_2O$ ($LH=N$ -formyl, N -acetyl, monochloroacetyl, trifluoroacetyl-*L*-phenylalanine, N -benzoyl monochloroacetyl, trichloroacetyl, trifluoroacetyl-*D,L*-alanine, N -benzoylglycine and N -benzoyl-*L*-leucine, $B=$ imidazole, 2-methylimidazole and 1,2-dimethylimidazole $n=2$; $X=0-6$) have been prepared and characterised with the help of various physical and spectroscopic techniques.

THE nickel(II) complexes with *N*-acetylglycine (1), *N*-benzoylglycine¹, *N*-acetyl-*DL*-valine², *N*-acetyl-tryptophane³, *N*-acetyl-*DL*-alanine⁴, *N*-acetyl-*DL*-leucine⁵ and their adducts have been reported. Magnetic moments and electronic spectra of the complexes are consistent with hexacoordinated nickel(II) with some distortion from the octahedral symmetry. Ir spectra agree with the coordination of the amino acids from the carboxyl group. Chromium(III) forms 1:3 (metal-ligand) green as well as purple complexes with glycine, alanine, valine and leucine. Ir spectra reveal the coordination through carboxylate and amino groups. The solid state reflectance spectra showed two bands⁶ around 17 000 and 23 000 cm^{-1} .

Experimental

All the *N*-acylamino acids were prepared, their purity was checked by tlc and were characterised by their m.ps. and ¹H nmr spectra. The *N*-acyl amino acids prepared along with their abbreviations used are: *N*-formyl-*L*-phenylalanine (For-PheH), *N*-benzoyl-*DL*-alanine (Bz-AlaH), *N*-benzoyl-glycine (Bz-GlyH), *N*-benzoyl-*L*-leucine (Bz-LeuH), monochloroacetyl-*DL*-alanine (MCA-AlaH), trichloroacetyl-*DL*-alanine (TCA-AlaH), trifluoroacetyl-*DL*-alanine (TFA-AlaH), *N*-acetyl-*L*-phenylalanine (Ac-PheH), monochloroacetyl-*L*-phenylalanine (MCA-PheH) and trifluoroacetyl-*L*-phenylalanine (TFA-PheH). Amines used were imidazole (Im), 2-methylimidazole (2-MeIm) and 1,2-dimethylimidazole (1,2-DimIm).

The amino acids like *L*-phenylalanine, *DL*-alanine, *L*-leucine (all Sisco), imidazole, 2-methylimidazole and 1,2-dimethylimidazole (all Sisco) and nickel nitrate, methanol, glycine, lead nitrate, EDTA (disod. salt), nitric acid (A.R.), hydrochloric acid (A.R.)

and sulphuric acid (all B.D.H.), trichloroacetic acid, chloroacetic acid, acetic anhydride, acetic acid, formic acid, benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and benzoyl chloride (E. Merk), trifluoroacetic acid (Ferah) were used. Except solvents all other reagents were used as such. The solvents were purified and dried by known method⁷.

Procedure: Trifluoroacetic anhydride⁸, chloroacetyl chloride and trichloroacetyl chloride⁹, *N*-formylamino acids¹⁰, *N*-acetylamino acid^{11,12}, *N*-benzoylamino acids^{13,14}, monochloroacetyl and trichloroacetyl amino acids¹⁵ and trifluoroacetyl amino acids¹⁶ were prepared by the known methods. Sodium salts of the *N*-acylamino acids were prepared¹⁷ and characterised by ir spectra.

Bis(*N*-acylamino-carboxylato)nickel(II) hydrates (NiL_2XH_2O): Freshly prepared nickel(II) hydroxide (~ 0.0012 mol) was added to a hot solution of the *N*-protected amino acid (0.002 mol) in methanol (50 ml) solvent. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for ~ 4 h. The unreacted nickel(II) hydroxide was removed by filtration. The resulting light green solution was evaporated on a water-bath to a semi-solid which was dried in a desiccator (sulphuric acid) for a few days. The powdered complexes were dried under reduced pressure.

Bis(amine)-bis(*N*-acylamino-carboxylato)nickel(II) hydrates ($NiL_2B_nXH_2O$) ($L=$ amino acid anion, $B=$ imidazole, 2-methylimidazole and 1,2-dimethylimidazole, $n=2$; $X=0-2$): The amine (~ 0.002 mol) was added to a solution of NiL_2XH_2O (0.001 mol) in methanol (50 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water for ~ 3 h. The solution was filtered and evaporated on a water-bath to a semi-solid. The resulting adduct was washed twice with diethyl ether, dried in a desiccator (sulphuric acid) for a few days, powdered and dried under reduced pressure.

Tetra(N-Acylaminocarboxylato)-μ-dihydroxodichromium(III) hydrates: A mixture of hexa-aquochromium(III) chloride (0.02 mol) and *N*-acylamino acid (0.04 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed over a water-bath for 0.5 h. After adding NaOH (0.06 mol) it was again refluxed for 6–7 h. The solution was then filtered while hot and evaporated on a water-bath to a semi-solid which was washed with hot water, dried in a sulphuric acid desiccator, powdered and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes with monochloroacetyl, trichloroacetyl and trifluoroacetyl-*DL*-alanine were prepared from chromium(III) nitrate nonahydrate in a similar manner.

Hexa(N-acylaminocarboxylato)dichromium(III) hydrates: A mixture of hexa-aquochromium(III) chloride (0.02 mol) and *N*-protected amino acids (0.062 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed over a water-bath for 0.5 h. Rest of the procedure followed was the same as given in the bis-type complexes.

The magnetic susceptibility at room temperature was measured by Gouy's method¹⁸. $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ was used as a calibrant¹⁹. Molar conductance of millimolar solutions in methanol was measured on a Toshniwal C101/02A conductivity bridge using a conventional dip type platinum electrode¹⁸. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-300 spectrophotometer, electron spectra on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer and esr spectra at room temperature on a Jeol FE-3XG X-band instrument. Elemental analysis data were obtained from the Regional Sophisticated and Instrumentation Centre, Chandigarh. The metal

ions were estimated volumetrically using EDTA. The melting points of the complexes were determined in capillaries and are uncorrected.

Results and Discussion

All the forty complexes and adducts (Table 1) of nickel(II) and fourteen complexes of chromium(III) in 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 ratios (metal-ligand) with the ligands are stable in air, except two nickel adducts of 1,2-dimethylimidazole with trifluoroacetyl-*DL*-alanine and trifluoroacetyl-*L*-phenylalanine and two chromium(III) complexes with MCA-AlaH and TFA-AlaH in the molar ratio 1 : 3 which are highly hygroscopic in air. These complexes are green to greyish except the complexes with For-PheH which are light purple and are soluble in polar solvents and insoluble in non-polar solvents. The molar conductance of the nickel(II) adducts is comparable to two ion electrolytes while chromium(III) complexes are non-electrolytes in methanol. The magnetic moment of the nickel(II) complexes is normal but that of the chromium(III) complexes is somewhat lower (3.09–3.77 B.M.) than the spin-only value (3.87 B.M.), except complex sl. no. 49 (Table 1). This may be due to partial spin-pairing via bridging groups indicating the dimeric nature of these complexes.

The N–H stretching vibration of the *N*-acylamino acids absorbs in the range 3 270–3 370 cm^{-1} while in the Ni^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes it absorbs at 3 280–3 420 and 3 260–3 400 cm^{-1} respectively, due to

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)		M. p. °C	μ_{eff} , B.M. (Temp., K)
		Nitrogen	Metal		
1.	$\text{Ni}(\text{For-Phe})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	5.58 (5.84)	11.90 (12.31)	215–16	3.31(291)
2.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Ala})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.90 (5.84)	12.20 (12.31)	210–11	2.89(313)
3.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Gly})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	5.89 (6.20)	12.70 (13.08)	231–33	2.96(313)
4.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Leu})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3.96 (4.95)	10.10 (10.47)	160–82	2.95(313)
5.	$\text{Ni}(\text{For-Phe})_2(\text{Im})_2$	13.97 (14.50)	10.20 (10.18)	105–07	3.18(291)
6.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Ala})_2(\text{Im})_2$	14.00 (14.50)	10.00 (10.18)	100–04	3.39(313)
7.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Gly})_2(\text{Im})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	14.84 (14.76)	10.40 (10.36)	97–99	2.89(313)
8.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Leu})_2(\text{Im})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	11.88 (12.33)	8.37 (8.66)	98–100	3.15(312)
9.	$\text{Ni}(\text{For-Phe})_2(2\text{MeIm})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	12.88 (13.44)	9.30 (9.44)	95–97	2.96(313)
10.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Ala})_2(2\text{MeIm})_2$	12.94 (13.84)	9.70 (9.71)	100–03	2.98(313)
11.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Gly})_2(2\text{MeIm})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	13.78 (14.07)	9.57 (9.88)	85–87	3.15(313)
12.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Leu})_2(2\text{MeIm})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	11.07 (11.84)	8.05 (8.32)	100–04	3.06(311)
13.	$\text{Ni}(\text{For-Phe})_2(1,2\text{-DiMeIm})_2$	12.79 (13.22)	9.00 (9.29)	77–80	2.95(313)
14.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Ala})_2(1,2\text{-DiMeIm})_2$	12.66 (13.22)	9.20 (9.29)	78–81	3.20(313)
15.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Gly})_2(1,2\text{-DiMeIm})_2$	12.91 (13.83)	9.80 (9.75)	81–84	3.26(307)
16.	$\text{Ni}(\text{Bz-Leu})_2(1,2\text{-DiMeIm})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	10.60 (11.39)	7.80 (8.00)	80–33	3.25(311)

(Table 1 contd.)

17.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	4.99 (5.52)	11.80 (11.63)	180-83	3.16(308)
18.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	4.51 (4.86)	9.90 (10.24)	108-10	2.96(308)
19.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ .2H ₂ O	3.95 (4.55)	9.50 (9.59)	115-20	3.22(308)
20.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	6.62 (6.60)	13.70 (13.90)	77-80	3.20(308)
21.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	4.42 (4.98)	10.80 (10.49)	212-15	3.16(308)
22.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ .2H ₂ O	6.02 (6.04)	12.70 (12.70)	112-14	3.35(308)
23.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	13.32 (13.83)	9.60 (9.71)	97-98	3.10(309)
24.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	11.66 (12.42)	8.70 (8.72)	89-90	3.16(309)
25.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (Im) ₂	11.05 (11.74)	8.60 (8.25)	85-87	3.20(309)
26.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	17.14 (15.49)	10.70 (10.88)	90-91	2.90(308)
27.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂	13.59 (12.68)	9.30 (8.91)	100-05	3.33(311)
28.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (Im) ₂ .H ₂ O	15.02 (14.45)	9.93 (10.15)	60-63	3.14(311)
29.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂	12.66 (13.22)	9.30 (9.29)	90-92	3.15(311)
30.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	11.39 (11.63)	7.86 (8.17)	73-75	2.95(311)
31.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂	11.17 (11.30)	8.00 (7.94)	70-72	3.17(309)
32.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	13.93 (14.73)	9.99 (10.35)	76-79	3.17(312)
33.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	10.87 (11.86)	8.55 (8.33)	75-77	3.08(312)
34.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (2MeIm) ₂	14.70 (14.21)	9.98 (9.98)	72-73	3.12(310)
35.	Ni(Ac-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	12.05 (12.66)	8.80 (8.89)	70-72	3.13(312)
36.	Ni(MCA-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	10.93 (11.47)	8.20 (8.06)	67-70	3.04(311)
37.	Ni(TFA-Phe) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ .2H ₂ O	— (10.38)	6.97 (7.31)	53-54	—
38.	Ni(MCA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ .2H ₂ O	13.72 (13.63)	9.60 (9.57)	75-78	3.12(311)
39.	Ni(TCA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂	11.09 (11.69)	8.20 (8.21)	87-89	3.31(312)
40.	Ni(TFA-Ala) ₂ (1,2-DiMeIm) ₂ .H ₂ O	— (13.14)	9.50 (9.26)	—	—
41.	[Cr(For-Phe) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	4.95 (5.99)	11.16 (11.04)	135-39	3.44(289)
42.	[Cr(Bz-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	5.65 (5.99)	11.30 (11.04)	165-68	3.31(289)
43.	[Cr(Bz-Gly) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	5.99 (6.32)	12.20 (11.73)	160-62	3.28(289)
44.	[Cr(Bz-Leu) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	4.66 (5.04)	9.50 (9.36)	135-36	3.20(289)
45.	[Cr(MCA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	6.80 (6.93)	11.90 (12.50)	118-20	3.53(309)
46.	[Cr(TCA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .4H ₂ O	3.59 (4.89)	8.60 (9.09)	120-22	3.57(309)
47.	[Cr(TFA-Ala) ₂ (OH)] ₂ .2H ₂ O	6.82 (6.15)	11.20 (11.42)	122-24	3.47(309)
48.	[Cr(For-Phe) ₂] ₂ .2H ₂ O	5.14 (6.50)	8.50 (8.04)	120-23	3.77(289)
49.	[Cr(Bz-Ala) ₂] ₂ .2H ₂ O	4.99 (6.50)	8.55 (8.04)	140-43	4.02(289)
50.	[Cr(Bz-Gly) ₂] ₂ .2H ₂ O	6.04 (6.95)	9.00 (8.60)	100-02	3.76(289)
51.	[Cr(Bz-Leu) ₂] ₂ .2H ₂ O	5.33 (5.44)	7.10 (6.73)	85-87	3.09(294)
52.	[Cr(MCA-Ala) ₂] ₂ .6H ₂ O	7.97 (7.69)	8.6 (8.67)	100-03	—
53.	[Cr(TCA-Ala) ₂] ₂ .6H ₂ O	4.67 (5.20)	6.3 (6.44)	98-100	3.61(309)
54.	[Cr(TFA-Ala) ₂] ₂ .6H ₂ O	7.32 (6.95)	7.3 (7.9)	101-03	—

different types of hydrogen bonding. The N-H bending mode, also called amide-II band, occurs at 1515–1557 cm⁻¹ in the *N*-acylamino acids. In the Ni^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes this band occurs at the same or slightly lower position (1510–1560 cm⁻¹) indicating the non-coordinating behaviour of the amide nitrogen. Amide-I band of the *N*-acylamino acids falls in the range 1595–1635 cm⁻¹ except in trifluoroacetyl and trichloroacetyl amino acids where it rises upto 1685–1700 cm⁻¹ due to electron-withdrawing inductive effect of three halogen atoms attached to the adjacent carbon atom. In the Ni^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes, the amide-I band is shifted to slightly lower or higher frequency due to hydrogen bonding.

Three criteria (i) $\Delta\nu$ difference between symmetric and asymmetric carboxylate stretching frequencies²⁰⁻²², (ii) direction of band shift (DBS)²³ and (iii) position of $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ ²⁴ are known in order to decide the coordination behaviour of carboxylate group. On the basis of these criteria, the carboxylate group coordinates as a chelating bidentate or bridging bidentate in the nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes. Coordination of amines through tertiary nitrogen is supported by the shift or disappearance of ir bands in adducts with respect to same band in free amines.

The electronic spectra of nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes show two absorption bands at 14800–16300 and 25000–26700 and 17000–18000 and 22700–24200 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Conclusion : An octahedral structure for the nickel(II) complexes is proposed with coordination from four oxygen atoms of two carboxylate group

and two oxygen atoms of water molecules in hydrate complexes or from oxygen atoms of two carboxylate group and two nitrogen atoms of amines in adducts (Fig 1). From the magnetic moment values and isotropic value of *g* an octahedral structure is proposed for all chromium complexes with coordination from four oxygen atoms of two carboxylate groups and two oxygen atoms of bridging hydroxyl groups (in 1 : 2) or two oxygen atoms of bridging carboxylate groups (in 1 : 3) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2

B = H₂O, Imidazole, 2-methylimidazole & 1,2-dimethylimidazole

Fig 1

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